

Role of Oxygen in the Photo-Oxidation of Diphenylamine

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Role of oxygen which decreases the quantum yield of carbazole formation through one step and increases it through another step in the photo-oxidation of diphenylamines has been examined for the formation of diphenylnitroxide in the benzophenone photosensitized oxidation of diphenylamine. The effect of passing oxygen is a composite effect consisting of increased oxygen concentration and mixing. Low intensity kinetics are found to be no different eliminating radical-radical reactions. The photo-oxidation rate in various solvents passes through a maximum with change in oxygen concentration suggesting oxygen induced deactivation step in the mechanism. $O_2(^1E_g^+ \text{ or } ^1\Delta_g)$ was generated *in situ* and non-formation of diphenylnitroxide establishes that singlet oxygen does not lead to nitroxide formation.

PARKER and Barnes¹ were the first to report the photo-oxidative cyclization of diphenylamine in solution to carbazole. In a later spectrophotometric study the effect of oxygen and butadiene on carbazole formation was examined². Oxygen inhibited the reaction rate but butadiene had no effect. Butadiene is a triplet state quencher and, therefore, the conclusion was that triplet diphenylamine is not responsible for the carbazole formation. Linschitz, *et al.*³, studied the same reaction by flash photolysis and confirmed that the transient species were not triplet diphenylamines. In more recent flash photolytic investigations the quantum yield of carbazole formation is found to pass through a maximum with change in oxygen and carbazole is confirmed to come from the triplet state^{4,5}. This can be taken to be the correct position in view of the nature of experiments and close fit of the studied variables in the kinetic expression based on the proposed mechanism.

On the other hand photo-oxidation of diphenylamine (DPA) particularly in the presence of sensitizers is known to lead to diphenyl nitroxide which also arises from electronically excited triplet state⁶⁻⁹. The presence of alcohols is known to enhance the reaction in the benzophenone (BP) sensitized systems^{7,8} and alcohols are expected to have higher concentrations of dissolved and complexed oxygen. Oxygen is supposed to effect the quantum yield of nitroxide formation and a detailed study of its effect which has not been undertaken so far is expected to reveal mechanistically important details. Hence the present investigation.

Experimental

Benzophenone (Bush, England) and diphenylamine (Riedel, Germany) were repeatedly crystallized to give sharp melting points. Solvents were analytical

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grade reagents and were freshly distilled before use. DPA has little absorption beyond 3300Å and benzophenone sensitization is commonly done with the emission from Hg lamps around 3650Å. The emission from a medium pressure Hanovia mercury lamp was filtered through 5 mm thick specially selected glass⁸ with cut off at 3300Å and 5% $CuSO_4$ in water which has maximum transmittance at 3700Å.

The cell consisted of a pyrex tube fitted with an inlet gas tube and a condenser to prevent evaporation.

Gases were taken from the cylinders and mixed in suitable proportions when necessary and monitored by precalibrated soap bubble flow meters. Before introducing the gases into the reaction cell, they were pre-saturated with the solvents.

In benzene the photolysed solution has an absorption spectrum which has been assigned to diphenylnitroxide and this has been confirmed as a product by esr⁷. Diphenylnitroxide has a shoulder at 4500Å and BP does not interfere at this wavelength. All the measurements were therefore made at this wavelength with a spectrophotometer keeping the unirradiated solution as reference.

Results and Discussion

The Figure 1 shows the effect of passing air for 30 mins before the reaction and continuing the flow during the photosensitization at different flow rates in benzene. The rate for higher flow rate is higher which shows that the reaction is strongly oxygen concentration dependent. Passing air also amounts to stirring of the solution and it was felt that the observed effect may be because of mixing. The solutions were stirred by bubbling of oxygen free nitrogen and also with a magnetic stirrer. It was observed that the air effect is a composite effect consisting of increased oxygen concentration and

mixing. The curves in Fig. 1 have higher slopes in the beginning. This is because of higher concentration of oxygen which is rapidly depleted and which is not all made up from air stream probably because of slow rate of its dissolution. This was confirmed by the observation of enhanced rate of reaction after interrupting light for 60 min in a run.

Fig. 1 Effect of flow rate of air in the system 0.20M BP + 0.02M DPA in benzene. \circ - \circ - \circ 8 ml/min; \square - \square - \square 30 ml/min; and \triangle - \triangle - \triangle 60 ml/min

When air is not passed the rate does not go on falling as would be expected on the basis of oxygen depletion argument. This is perhaps due to the fact that in the absence of oxygen some carbinol^{10a} is formed which has absorbance at the monitoring wavelength. Indeed the spectrum in the visible region of the aerated and deaerated runs were somewhat different. No absorbance at 4300A was observed even on prolonged irradiation of deaerated solutions of either BP or DPA alone.

In order to scan the initial stages of the reaction, photolyses were done at decreased light intensities. In benzene the rate is linear to start with and some tapering off of the rate is observed which can be due to depletion of oxygen and not due to any secondary reactions of the product. In pure isopropanol where the product is formed in much higher yield, no such lowering of the rate is observed.

The effect of concentration of oxygen in different solvents was next examined. The results are shown in Figs. 2-4. The plot is linear in acetone and nearly linear in isopropanol. The rate passes through a maximum with increase in oxygen concentration in all the three solvents. The rates with pure oxygen are lower. The oxidation in alcohols is more complicated^{10b} but it is not likely to interfere in the interpretation of oxygen effect since the rates are almost linear and we are measuring the total absorbance. At any rate the conclusions are valid for at least non-hydroxylic solvents.

Fig. 2. Effect of oxygen concentration in the system 0.20M BP + 0.02M DPA in benzene with high light intensity. \circ - \circ - \circ $N_2:O_2::10:1$; \triangle - \triangle - \triangle O_2 ; and \square - \square - \square $N_2:O_2::1:1$ (total gas flow rate = 22 ml/min.).

In BP and dye sensitized reactions, amines have been shown to react mostly without the participation of singlet oxygen¹¹⁻¹³. DPA, however, is different. From Stern-Volmer plots (quenching rate constant for BP+DPA) it appears that BP is transferring energy rather than abstracting hydrogen¹⁴. In some prolonged runs BP was monitored at carbonyl stretching frequency of 1670 cm⁻¹ by i.r. in 5 mm long cells. No disappearance of BP was detected which confirms the said results. Therefore the possibility of direct energy transfer (step 1);

should be considered. There is no restriction on this process. The energy gap is large (31.6 kcal for ¹Σ_g+O₂) and at the best the process can be slow though in view of the condensed phase it need not be too slow. The results in the presence and absence of oxygen in BP systems are known to be different^{15,16}. For the reduction of BP by isopropanol, quantum yield of acetone formation is independent of oxygen concentration but the yield of benzopinacol is reduced from almost unity in an oxygen free system to zero when the solution is saturated with oxygen. In the latter case significant yields of hydrogen peroxide were obtained but the BP was not used up in the reaction. These kinetic observations are compatible with initial energy transfer to oxygen [process (1)].

Deactivation of triplets by oxygen is well established in many cases so much so that this deactivation has been used as a test of triplet state¹⁷⁻²⁰. In the

carbazole formation from direct DPA photolysis the observed maximum with increase in oxygen concentration has also been explained through deactivation of triplets by oxygen^{21,5}. The following mechanism is proposed to account for the results on the effect of oxygen :

Hydrogen peroxide was detected in these systems but all attempts to measure it failed to yield reproducible results. The rate constant for hydrogen abstraction from isopropanol (reaction 6);

is 6 × 10⁵ M⁻¹ sec⁻¹ (ref. 22), and the rate for diffusion controlled energy transfer is of the order of 10⁹ M⁻¹ sec⁻¹. It is, therefore, expected that in the presence of excess of isopropanol, abstraction may also take place alongwith energy transfer. Indeed it does. The rate of the reaction which increases initially with the increase of concentration of isopropanol was observed to drop at concentration higher than 7M. This effect was not observed in methanol as expected.

fig. 3. Oxygen effect on the oxide formation in BP sensitized photo-oxidation of DPA in acetone. -○-○- O₂; -△-△- N₂ : O₂ :: 1 : 1; and -□-□- N₂ : O₂ :: 10 : 1 (total gas flow rate = 22 ml/min.).

Fig. 4. Effect of oxygen concentration in the system 0.20M BP+0.02M DPA in isopropanol. $\ominus\text{-}\ominus$ O_2 ; $\text{-}\square\text{-}\square$ $\text{N}_2 : \text{O}_2 :: 10 : 1$; and $\text{-}\triangle\text{-}\triangle$ $\text{N}_2 : \text{O}_2 :: 1 : 1$ (total gas flow rate = 22 ml/min.).

The question which remains to be answered is whether singlet oxygen gives rise to nitroxide. A direct test would be to compare the products and kinetics of the present systems with the systems in which singlet oxygen is produced *in situ* by a known method. This is possible and was done through the reaction of $\text{NaOCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ ²³ in methanol/water mixtures as solvent. Diphenylnitroxide was not formed but another coloured product which after extraction with ether, separated on column chromatography (Al_2O_3 ; eluent = benzene). It can therefore be concluded that singlet oxygen does not lead to diphenylnitroxide.

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